

Synthesis, Characterization and *In-Silico* Studies of Novel Thiazolidine Analogues and Their Biological Evaluation as Potential Anti-Leishmanial Agents

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ABSTRACT

In this investigation, five Schiff bases (SB-1 to SB-5) were synthesized via condensation reactions between different aldehydes and primary amines, subsequently serving as intermediates for the synthesis of four thiazolidine derivatives (TH-1 to TH-5) through cyclization with cysteine. Structural elucidation was confirmed using advanced spectroscopic techniques.

In vitro assays revealed notable anti-promastigote activity of SB-2, SB-4, and SB-5 against *Leishmania major*, with IC₅₀ values of [9.75±0.03] μM, [3.17±0.01] μM, and [6.98±0.06] μM, respectively. Comparable activity was observed against *Leishmania tropica*, with IC₅₀ values of [9.75±0.04] μM, [9.13±0.01] μM, and [10.72±0.08] μM. Likewise, thiazolidine derivatives TH-1, TH-3, and TH-4 demonstrated exceptional anti-promastigote efficacy against *L. major*, with IC₅₀ values of [2.26±0.02] μM, [1.18±0.02] μM, and [1.36±0.01] μM, respectively.

The anti-amastigote activity of SB-2, SB-4, SB-5, TH-1, TH-3, and TH-4 against *L. tropica* yielded IC₅₀ values of [6.31±0.07] μM, [2.32±0.03] μM, [3.30±0.01] μM, [2.80±0.07] μM, [8.21±0.02] μM, and [1.82±0.03] μM, respectively. Enzyme inhibition assays identified RWT-1, RWT-2, and RWT-4 as potent inhibitors of human dihydrofolate reductase (hDHFR), with IC₅₀ values of [5.30±0.4] μM, [1.08±0.2] μM, and [2.08±0.6] μM, respectively.

In silico molecular docking studies, targeting key *Leishmania* enzymes (GAPDH, TR, and GR), indicated high binding affinities for SB-5 (-7.91 kcal/mol), SB-4 (-7.64 kcal/mol), SB-2 (-7.03 kcal/mol), TH-4 (-7.18 kcal/mol), TH-1 (-6.97 kcal/mol), and TH-3 (-6.84 kcal/mol).

These compelling results underscore the potential of SB-2, SB-4, SB-5, TH-1, TH-3, and TH-4 as promising candidates for leishmaniasis treatment, meriting further exploration.

Keywords

Leishmania, Schiff bases, Thiazolidine derivatives, Molecular docking, Enzyme assays, Pharmacokinetic studies, toxicological studies, SAR (Structure-Activity Relationship), SB (Schiff Base), TH (Thiazolidine)

1 Introduction

Leishmaniasis is a critical yet neglected tropical disease caused by protozoan parasites of the genus *Leishmania*, transmitted to humans via the bite of infected female phlebotomine sandflies. This disease manifests in several clinical forms, including cutaneous leishmaniasis, which results in skin ulcers; mucocutaneous leishmaniasis, which damages mucous membranes; and visceral leishmaniasis (kala-azar), a severe form that targets vital organs such as the liver, spleen, and bone marrow. *Leishmania donovani* and *Leishmania infantum* are primarily responsible for visceral leishmaniasis, while *Leishmania major*, *Leishmania tropica*, and *Leishmania braziliensis* are predominantly linked to cutaneous and mucocutaneous leishmaniasis. The distinct geographical distribution of each species complicates both global and regional efforts to control and manage the disease (Alvar et al., 2021).

Leishmaniasis is endemic in 98 countries, with more than 350 million individuals at risk globally. The World Health Organization estimates that between 700,000 to 1 million new cases occur annually, resulting in approximately 20,000 to 30,000 deaths, primarily due to visceral leishmaniasis. In Pakistan, the disease presents a considerable public health burden, particularly in the provinces of Baluchistan, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, and Sindh, where frequent outbreaks have been reported. The incidence of leishmaniasis is on the rise, with cutaneous leishmaniasis being the most prevalent form. Inadequate surveillance, insufficient control measures, and limited healthcare access further exacerbate the situation, leading to substantial morbidity and mortality (Nabi et al., 2020).

The pathogenesis of leishmaniasis involves the parasite's ability to subvert the host's immune response and replicate within macrophages. Several key enzymes are critical to the survival and virulence of *Leishmania* parasites, including glyceraldehyde-3-phosphate dehydrogenase (GAPDH), trypanothione reductase (TR), and glutathione reductase (GR). These enzymes are integral to metabolic pathways that support the parasite's energy production and detoxification mechanisms. Targeting these enzymes through rational drug design represents a promising strategy for developing novel therapeutic agents against leishmaniasis. Inhibiting

these enzymes disrupts the parasite's life cycle, leading to its eventual eradication from the host (Bhattacharya et al., 2021).

Current therapeutic options for leishmaniasis include antimonial compounds such as sodium stibogluconate and meglumine antimoniate, amphotericin B, miltefosine, and paromomycin. Although these treatments demonstrate efficacy, they are marred by significant limitations and adverse side effects. Antimonial drugs are associated with severe cardiotoxicity and hepatotoxicity, while amphotericin B is known to cause nephrotoxicity and infusion-related reactions. Miltefosine, despite being an oral option, is linked to gastrointestinal disturbances and teratogenicity, limiting its use in pregnant women. Thus, there remains an urgent need for safer, more effective therapeutic interventions to combat leishmanial Paromomycin, used for both visceral and cutaneous forms, can cause ototoxicity and nephrotoxicity. Furthermore, the emergence of drug-resistant *Leishmania* strains, lengthy treatment regimens, and the high cost of these therapies pose substantial challenges, emphasizing the urgent need for new, safer, and more effective anti-leishmanial agents (Sundar & Chakravarty, 2021)

Schiff bases are a distinguished class of organic compounds, characterized by the presence of an azomethine group ($-\text{CH}=\text{N}-$), formed through the condensation reaction between primary amines and carbonyl compounds, typically aldehydes or ketones. These compounds are renowned for their structural versatility, which permits extensive functional group modifications, thereby enhancing their chemical and biological properties. Schiff bases demonstrate a broad spectrum of biological activities, encompassing antimicrobial, antiviral, anticancer, and anti-inflammatory effects. Moreover, their capacity to form stable complexes with metal ions further amplifies their therapeutic potential. The azomethine linkage in Schiff bases plays a pivotal role in facilitating hydrogen bonding and other molecular interactions with biological targets, enabling them to modulate enzyme activity and influence cellular processes effectively (Sharma et al., 2020).

In the sphere of anti-leishmanial research, Schiff bases serve as vital intermediates in the synthesis of thiazolidine derivatives. These derivatives are formed through the cyclization of Schiff bases with cysteine, yielding a five-membered heterocyclic ring that contains both sulfur and nitrogen atoms. Thiazolidine derivatives have garnered significant attention for their enhanced stability and pronounced bioactivity. Their ability to interact with essential enzymes of *Leishmania* parasites, such as glyceraldehyde-3-phosphate dehydrogenase (GAPDH), trypanothione reductase (TR), and glutathione reductase (GR), is of particular

importance. These interactions typically involve the binding of thiazolidine derivatives to the active sites of these enzymes, thereby inhibiting their function and disrupting crucial metabolic pathways vital for parasite survival. This mechanism underscores the potential of Schiff bases and their thiazolidine derivatives as potent anti-leishmanial agents, capable of targeting and neutralizing key enzymatic functions within the parasite (Patel et al., 2020).

Thiazolidine derivatives are a class of heterocyclic compounds defined by a five-membered ring structure containing sulfur and nitrogen atoms. These compounds are synthesized via the cyclization of Schiff bases with thiol-containing agents such as cysteine. The unique structural framework of thiazolidines imparts substantial chemical stability, while their ability to engage in diverse chemical reactions renders them invaluable intermediates in medicinal chemistry. The sulfur and nitrogen atoms within the ring facilitate hydrogen bonding and other non-covalent interactions, thereby enhancing their binding affinity to biological targets. This structural adaptability lends itself to a wide range of biological activities, including antimicrobial, antifungal, anti-inflammatory, and anticancer properties, making thiazolidine derivatives highly attractive candidates for drug development (Patel et al., 2020).

In the context of anti-leishmanial research, thiazolidine derivatives have exhibited exceptional potential due to their ability to selectively target and inhibit vital enzymes in *Leishmania* parasites. Enzymes such as glyceraldehyde-3-phosphate dehydrogenase (GAPDH), trypanothione reductase (TR), and glutathione reductase (GR) are indispensable for the parasite's metabolic pathways and overall survival. Thiazolidine derivatives effectively bind to the active sites of these enzymes, thereby disrupting their activity and impairing the parasite's ability to thrive. Compared to conventional treatments, thiazolidine derivatives offer several advantages, including potentially lower toxicity, minimized side effects, and a reduced risk of developing drug resistance. Their specificity in targeting leishmanial enzymes, while sparing human enzymes, highlights their therapeutic superiority, establishing them as safer and more effective alternatives to traditional anti-leishmanial therapies (Bhattacharya et al., 2021).

2 Experimental

2.1 Materials and Method

Chemicals which were used during the reactions are: 4-(Diethyl amino)-2-hydroxybenzaldehyde (98%), 4-Nitro-1, 2-phenylenediamine (97%), 1-naphthylamine (97%),

2, 4, 6-trimethylamine (97%), aniline (98%), 1, 4-phenyldiamine (97%) and thioglycolic acid (97%). Analytical-grade solvents such as ethanol, methanol, ethyl acetate, n-hexane, dichloromethane, acetone, and chloroform were employed without any purification. The Japan ATY 224 electronic analytical balance was used to weigh the chemicals. TLC was taken on a regular basis and the reaction's progress was observed under a UV lamp. The various solvents in reaction mixtures were evaporated using the Bauchi Rota vapor R-210. Melting points of synthesized products were determined using the Melting Point device SMP10. The functional groups found in the final products were examined using an ATR model ALPHA 20488-equipped FT-IR. A 400 MHz BRUKER spectrometer was used for the $^1\text{H-NMR}$ analysis, with DMSO serving as the solvent.

2.2 Synthetic Procedure

General Procedure

Five Schiff bases (**S.B-1 to S.B-5**) were synthesized by reacting 4-(diethylamino)-2-hydroxybenzaldehyde (98%), with five different primary amines in 1; 1 (10mmol each) for 6-9 hours under reflux conditions. Whatman filter paper was used to filter precipitates that were washed many times by using methanol, ethanol, and ethyl- acetate and isolated. Synthesized Schiff base (1mmol) was then dissolved in toluene (50 mL) and added to thioglycolic acid (0.9 mL; 1.3 eq., 92 g/mol, $d=1.32$ g/mL) to synthesize five thiazolidine compounds (**TH-1-TH-5**). The Dean stark trap was used to reflux the resultant solution. TLC was used to monitor progress of reaction. Brine and a 3% NaHCO_3 solution (4×10 mL) were used to wash the product. The organic layer was dried over Na_2SO_4 then concentrated in vacuo. The products were re-crystallized in ethanol.

Figure 1: General scheme for the synthesis of Schiff base derived thiazolidine compounds.

2.3 Anti-Leishmanial Activity (Anti-promastigote & Anti-amastigote Activity)

The anti-amastigote and anti-promastigote activities of the synthesized compounds were meticulously evaluated using well-established *in vitro* protocols. Promastigotes of *Leishmania* were cultured in RPMI-1640 medium supplemented with 10% fetal bovine serum, maintained at a temperature of 26°C. To assess anti-promastigote activity, varying concentrations of the synthesized compounds were introduced into the promastigote cultures, and their viability was analyzed after 72 hours using the MTT assay.

For the anti-amastigote activity, murine macrophages were infected with *Leishmania* promastigotes, allowing the parasites to undergo transformation into intracellular amastigotes. Following infection, the compounds were administered at different concentrations, and the infected macrophages were incubated at 37°C with 5% CO₂ for 72 hours. The efficacy of the compounds was assessed by microscopically determining the number of viable amastigotes per macrophage after Giemsa staining. The IC₅₀ values were calculated for both assays to quantify the potency of the compounds against *Leishmania*, providing critical insights into their potential therapeutic efficacy.

2.4 Enzyme Assay (hDHFR Assay)

The assay for evaluating dihydrofolate reductase (DHFR) enzyme inhibition involves several meticulous steps to determine the efficacy of test compounds. Initially, the DHFR enzyme is obtained either commercially or via recombinant expression techniques. Substrate solutions of dihydrofolate (DHF) and NADPH are prepared and introduced into an assay buffer containing Tris-HCl, NaCl, and MgCl₂ to establish optimal conditions for enzymatic activity.

In a 96-well plate, the assay commences with the addition of DHF and NADPH solutions, followed by the test compounds at various concentrations. Positive (methotrexate) and negative (DMSO) controls are also included. After the plate setup, the enzymatic reaction is initiated by adding the DHFR enzyme solution, achieving a final concentration of 10 nM per well.

The mixture is gently agitated and incubated at 25°C for 30 minutes to allow the enzyme-catalyzed reactions to proceed. Post-incubation, enzyme activity is evaluated by measuring changes in absorbance over time, which reflects the rate of product formation. By comparing the enzyme activity in the presence of test compounds against the controls, inhibition levels

are determined. This assessment provides valuable insights into the potential of the compounds as DHFR enzyme inhibitors, informing their prospective therapeutic applications.

2.5 *In-Silico* Studies

Molecular docking studies utilizing AutoDock Vina and Discovery Studio are pivotal for identifying efficacious treatments for Leishmania infections. These simulations predict the interaction of compounds with critical enzymes such as dihydrofolate reductase (DHFR), trypanothione reductase (TR), glutathione reductase (GR), and glyceraldehyde-3-phosphate dehydrogenase (GAPDH) at the molecular level. This information is instrumental in developing potent drugs with specific binding affinities and minimizing resistance risks.

In silico pharmacokinetic analyses performed using Swiss ADME and LabWare software assess the absorption, distribution, metabolism, and excretion (ADME) properties of potential drug candidates. These evaluations are crucial for optimizing bioavailability and formulating appropriate dosing strategies for preclinical and clinical studies.

Simultaneously, toxicological assessments conducted with Tox-21 and LabWare software evaluate the safety profiles of these compounds, ensuring compliance with regulatory standards and confirming their suitability for clinical advancement. These computational methodologies significantly expedite the drug discovery and development process, providing critical insights necessary for the advancement of effective therapies against leishmaniasis.

3 Results

3.1 Physical Analysis

The physical data of all the Schiff bases regarding molecular weight, atom economy, physical appearance, melting points, and yield are written in Table 1.

Table 1: Physical Data of Schiff bases (S.B-1-S. B-5).

Sr. No	Molecular Weight (g/mol)	Physical Appearance	Atom Economy	Melting Point (°C)	Yield (%)
SB-1	503	Orange powder	94	205	85
SB-2	309	Yellow crystals	93.7	100	80
SB-3	283	Orange solid	94	276	93
SB-4	318	Green solid	94	125	84
SB-5	268	Yellow crystals	93.7	199	85

The physical data of all the synthesized thiazolidine compounds regarding molecular weight, atom economy, physical appearance, melting points, and yield are written in Table 2.

Table 2: Physical Data of synthesized thiazolidine (TH-1- TH-5).

Sr. No	Molecular Weight (g/mol)	Physical Appearance	Atom Economy	Melting Point (°C)	Yield (%)
TH-1	653	Orange powder	94	200	85
TH-2	384	Yellow crystals	93.7	110	80
TH-3	357	Orange solid	94	270	93
TH-4	392	Green solid	94	123	84
TH-5	318	Yellow crystals	93.7	211	85

3.2 Spectroscopic Analysis

((4-Nitro-1, 2-phenylene) bis (azaneylylidene)) bis (methanelylidene) bis (3-(diethyl amino) phenol) [SB-1]

Reaction time: 6hr, Molecular formula: C₂₈H₃₃N₅O₄. TLC system [25% ethyl acetate: hexane], FTIR (V_{max} , cm^{-1}): 3329(O-H), 3000 (C-H), 1577(C=N), 1413 (C=C), 1518 (NO₂), 1327 (C-N), 1130 (C-O), ¹H-NMR: 1.15 (6H, t, $J = 7$, H_a), 3.55 (4H, q, $J = 7$, H_b), 6.1 (1H,

d, $J = 2$, H_c), 6.33(1H, dd, $J = 2.5$, 9, H_d), 6.5(1H, s, H_e), 6.8 (1H, d, $J = 9$, H_f), 7.5(1H, d, $J = 9$, H_g), 7.85 (1H, d, $J = 2.5$, H_h), 7.9 (1H, dd, $J = 2.5$, 8.5, H_i), 8.7 (1H, s, H_j).

3, 3'-(4-nitro-1, 2-phenylene) bis (2-(4-(diethyl amino)-2-hydroxyphenyl) thiazolidin-4-one) [TH-1]

Reaction time: 6hr, Molecular formula: C₃₂H₃₉N₅O₆S₂, TLC system [25% ethyl acetate: hexane], FTIR (V_{max} , cm⁻¹): 3350 (O-H), 3070, 2880 (C-H), 1670 (C=O), 1510 (C=C), 1259 (C-N), 670 (C-S). ¹H-NMR: 1.15 (12H, t, $J = 6$, H_a), 3.40 (2H, s, H_b), 3.45 (8H, q, $J = 6$, H_c), 3.65(2H, s, H_d), 5.85(1H, s, H_e), 6.01 (1H, s, H_f), 6.25(2H, s, H_g), 6.41 (2H, m, H_h), 6.61 (1H, s, H_i), 6.79 (1H, s, H_j), 7.30 (1H, d, $J = 6$, H_k), 7.39 (1H, d, $J = 6.8$, H_l), 7.45 (1H, d, $J = 6.8$, H_m), 7.99 (1H, d, $J = 2$, H_n), 8.15 (1H, d, $J = 6$, H_o).

5-(Diethyl amino)-2-((mesityl imino) methyl) phenol [SB-2]

Reaction time: 6hr, Molecular formula: C₂₁H₂₇NO, TLC system: [20% ethyl acetate: hexane], FTIR (V_{max} , cm⁻¹) 3500(O-H), 2968(C-H), 1596(C=N), 1520(C=C), 1299 (C-N), 1193 (C-O). ¹H-NMR: 1.1 (6H, t, $J = 6.5$, H_a), 2.1 (6H, s, H_b), 2.2 (3H, s, H_c), 3.5(4H, q, $J = 6.5$, H_d), 6.1(1H, s, H_e), 6.3 (1H, d, $J = 6.5$, H_f), 6.8 (2H, s, H_g), 7.3 (1H, d, $J = 6.5$, H_h), 8.3 (1H, s, H_i).

2-(4-(diethyl amino)-2-hydroxyphenyl)-3-mesitylthiazolidin-4-one [TH-2]

Reaction time: 6hr, Molecular formula: C₂₂H₂₈N₂O₂S, TLC system [25% ethyl acetate: hexane], FTIR (V_{max} , cm⁻¹) 3390 (O-H), 3049 (C-H), 1655 (C=O), 1503 (C=C), 1291 (C-N), 722 (C-S). ¹H-NMR: (DMSO-d₆, 400 MHz), (chemical shift (ppm), coupling constant MHz): 1.66 (6H, t, $J = 6$, H_a), 2.19 (6H, s, H_b), 2.26 (3H, s, H_c), 3.45 (4H, d, $J = 6$, H_d), 3.51 (2H, s, H_e), 6.01 (1H, s, H_f), 6.23 (1H, d, $J = 1.6$, H_g), 6.45 (1H, d, $J = 6.4$, H_h), 6.62 (1H, s, H_i), 6.99 (2H, s, H_j), 7.47 (1H, d, $J = 6$, H_k).

2-(((4-aminophenyl) imino) methyl)-5-(diethyl amino) phenol [SB-3]

Reaction time: 7hr, Molecular formula: C₁₇H₂₁N₃O. TLC system: [20% ethyl acetate: hexane], FTIR (V_{max} , cm⁻¹) 3350 (NH₂), 2950 (C-H), 1598 (C=N), 1520(C=C), 1305 (C-N), 1193 (C-O). ¹H-NMR: (DMSO-d₆, 400 MHz), (chemical shift (ppm), coupling constant MHz): 1.15 (6H, t, $J = 9.6$, H_a), 3.45 (4H, q, $J = 9.6$, H_b), 5.05 (2H, s, H_c), 5.95 (1H, s, H_d), 6.05 (1H, s, H_e), 6.35 (1H, dd, $J = 2.4$, 5.6, H_f), 6.75 (2H, d, $J = 8.2$, H_g), 6.85 (2H, d, $J = 8.4$, H_h), 7.41 (1H, dd, $J = 2$, 6, H_i), 8.09 (1H, s, H_j).

3-(4-aminophenyl)-2-(4-(diethyl amino)-2-hydroxyphenyl) thiazolidin-4-one [TH-3]

Reaction time: 6hr, Molecular formula: $C_{19}H_{23}N_3O_2S$, TLC system [20% ethyl acetate: hexane], FTIR (V_{max} , cm^{-1}) 3380 (NH₂), 2950 (C-H), 1680 (C=N), 1510(C=C), 1265 (C-N), 745 (C-S). ¹H-NMR: (DMSO-d₆, 400 MHz), (chemical shift (ppm), coupling constant MHz): 1.25 (6H, t, $J = 8$, H_a), 3.35 (2H, d, $J = 2.8$, H_b), 3.45 (4H, q, $J = 6$ H_c), 4.85 (2H, dd, $J = 2.4$, 6, H_d), 6.07 (1H, s, H_e), 6.36 (1H, d, $J = 1.6$ H_f), 6.49 (1H, d, $J = 6$, H_g), 6.60 (1H, s, H_h), 6.65 (2H, d, $J = 6$ H_i), 7.36 (2H, d, $J = 6$ H_j), 7.47 (1H, d, $J = 6.4$ H_k).

5-(Diethyl amino)-2-(naphthalen-1-ylimini) methyl phenol [SB-4]

Reaction time: 6hr, Molecular formula: $C_{21}H_{22}N_2O$ TLC system: [20% ethyl acetate: hexane], 20%, FTIR (V_{max} , cm^{-1}) 3100(O-H), 2964(C-H), 1619(C=N), 1566(C=C), 1343-1244 (C-N), 1222 (C-O), ¹H-NMR: 1.3 (6H, t, $J = 6.9$, H_a), 3.5 (4H, q, $J = 6.9$, H_b), 6.34 (2H, m, H_c), 7.2(1H, dd, $J = 7.2$, 0.6, H_d), 7.3 (1H, m, H_e), 7.5 (3H, m, H_f), 7.75 (1H, d, $J = 9$, $J = 9$, H_g), 7.9 (1H, m, H_h), 8.38 (1H, m, H_i), 8.5 (1H, s, H_j).

2-(4-(diethyl amino)-2-hydroxyphenyl)-3-(naphthalen-1-yl) thiazolidin-4-one [TH-4]

Reaction time: 6hr, Molecular formula: $C_{23}H_{24}N_2O_2S$, TLC system [20% ethyl acetate: hexane], FTIR (V_{max} , cm^{-1}) 3439 (O-H), 2950 (C-H), 1665 (C=O), 1498 (C=C), 1290 (C-N), 726 (C-S). ¹H-NMR: (DMSO-d₆, 400 MHz), (chemical shift (ppm), coupling constant MHz): 1.16 (6H, t, $J = 6$, H_a), 3.40 (2H, d, $J = 2$, H_b), 3.45 (4H, q, $J = 6$ H_c), 6.04 (1H, s, H_d), 6.25 (1H, d, $J = 1.6$, H_e), 6.45 (1H, dd, $J = 1.6$, 6, H_f), 6.62 (1H, s, H_g), 7.38 (1H, d, $J = 6$ H_h), 7.45 (1H, d, $J = 6.4$ H_i), 7.50 (3H, m, H_j), 7.75 (1H, d, $J = 6$, H_k), 7.85 (1H, d, $J = 6.8$, H_l), 8.02 (1H, d, $J = 6$, H_m).

5-(Diethyl amino)-2-((phenyl imino) methyl) phenol [SB-5]

Reaction time: 7hr, Molecular formula: $C_{17}H_{20}N_2O$, TLC system: [20% ethyl acetate: hexane], FTIR (V_{max} , cm^{-1}): 2972 (C-H), 1580(C=N), 1516 (C=C), 1340(C-N), 1134 (C-O), ¹H-NMR: (DMSO-d₆, 400 MHz), (chemical shift (ppm), coupling constant MHz): 1.15 (6H, t, $J = 6.4$, H_a), 3.45 (4H, q, $J = 6.4$, H_b), 5.01 (1H, s, H_c), 6.01 (1H, s, H_d), 6.40 (1H, d, $J = 6.4$, H_e), 6.95 (2H, m, H_f), 7.12 (3H, m, H_g), 7.20 (1H, s, H_h), 7.45 (1H, d, $J = 6$, H_i).

2-(4-(diethylamino)-2-hydroxyphenyl)-3-phenylthiazolidin-4-one [TH-5]

Reaction time: 6hr, Molecular formula: $C_{18}H_{22}N_2O_2S$, TLC system [25% ethyl acetate: hexane], FTIR (V_{max} , cm^{-1}) 3300 (O-H), 2018 (C-H), 1682 (C=O), 1493 (C=C), 1205 (C-N),

681 (C-S). $^1\text{H-NMR}$: (DMSO- d_6 , 400 MHz), (chemical shift (ppm), coupling constant MHz): 1.17 (6H, t, $J = 6.8$, H_a), 3.27 (2H, d, $J = 3.6$, H_b), 3.42 (4H, q, $J = 6$ H_c), 6.02 (1H, s, H_d), 6.32 (1H, d, , $J = 1.6$ H_e), 6.49 (1H, d, $J = 6$ H_f), 6.61 (1H, s, H_g), 7.31 (2H, d, , $J = 6$, H_h), 7.39 (1H, m, H_i), 7.45 (3H, m, H_j).

3.2 Biological Assays

3.2.1 Anti-Promastigotes Activity

Compounds	IC ₅₀ μm/ml <i>L.Major</i>	IC ₅₀ μm/ml <i>L.tropica</i>
SB-1	16.55±0.08	22.20±0.01
SB-2	9.75±0.03	9.75±0.04
SB-3	27.18±0.01	36.02±0.06
SB-4	3.17±0.01	9.13±0.01
SB-5	6.98±0.06	10.72±0.08
TH-1	2.26±0.02	-
TH-2	28.12±0.03	-
TH-3	1.18±0.02	-
TH-4	1.36±0.01	-
TH-5	5.66±0.07	-

3.2.2 Anti-Amastigotes Activity

Compounds/ Sample SB-1—SB-5	IC ₅₀ μg/ml
SB-1	38.80±0.02
SB-2	6.31±0.07
SB-3	12.31±0.02
SB-4	2.32±0.03
SB-5	3.30±0.01
Standarad AMP.B	2.90±0.01

TH-1 TO TH-4	Antileishmanial activity (Promastigotes) IC ₅₀ (μM)
	L. major
TH-1	2.80 ± 0.07
TH-2	19.55 ± 0.01
TH-3	8.21 ± 0.02
TH-4	1.82 ± 0.03
TH-5	16.50 ± 0.01
Amphotericin B (Ve+)	0.60 ± 0.05
Sodium Stibogluconate (Ve+)	-
DMSO (Ve-)	-

3.2.3 *In-Vitro* hDHFR Activity

TH SERIES	hDHFR IC ₅₀ (Mm)
TH-1	5.30 ± 0.4
TH-2	8.22 ± 0.2
TH-3	1.08 ± 0.2
TH-4	2.08 ± 0.6
TH-5	9.66 ± 0.2
Methotrexate	0.005

3.3 Molecular Docking Studies

3.3.1 Docking Studies Against GAPDH

S#	Ligand Interaction	Docking Score Kcal/mol	A.A residues
1	SB-1	-6.595 Kcal/mol	D:VAL219 :- 4.24661 Å A:ARG58 :- 4.88737 Å C:VAL55 :- 4.75663 Å
2	SB-2	-6.973 Kcal/mol	:THR54 :- O 3.51045 Å B:ALA299 :- 4.11812 Å D:PRO253 :- 4.29265 Å

3	SB-3	-5.769 Kcal/mol	F:GLY11:N :- 3.06137 Å F:ALA90:CB - :UNL1 :- 3.83821 Å F:THR111:CG2 - :UNL1 :- 3.84384 Å
4	SB-4	-7.499 Kcal/mol	B:THR197:CB :- 3.6569 Å B:PHE114 :- 5.00251 Å B:ARG12 :- 5.00751 Å B:ILE13 :- 4.82815 Å
5	SB-5	-7.816 Kcal/mol	A:ARG249:NH2 :- 3.08736 Å A:ASN335:ND2 :- 3.01541 Å A:ILE13 :- 4.83572 Å
6	TH-1	-7.548 Kcal/mol	B:THR54:O :- 2.12709 Å B:ILE302:CG2 :- 3.85871 Å D:ILE302 :- 4.09779 Å
7	TH-2	-6.248 Kcal/mol	A:ILE13 :- 3.85763 Å A:MET16 :- 4.49648 Å A:ARG249:NH2:- 4.68972 Å
8	TH-3	-7.343 Kcal/mol	F:SER165:OG :- 3.18458 Å F:CYS166:SG :- 4.11997 Å F:GLY227:N :- 3.77317 Å
9	TH-4	-7.753 Kcal/mol	A:TYR339 :- 4.83784 Å A:PRO136 :- 4.05624 Å A:SER165:CB :- 3.49071 Å A:PRO136 :- 4.05624 Å
10	TH-5	-7.078 Kcal/mol	B:ILE302 :- 5.31046 Å D:ILE302 :- 5.47497 Å D:ILE302 :- 5.45502 Å D:ASN303:ND2 :- 3.82681 Å

From this table it is clear that SB-5& TH- 4 have the highest docking scores among all.

2D & 3D Animation of SB5 & TH4

3.3.2 Docking Studies against Glutathione Reductase (GR)

S#	Ligand Interaction	Docking Score Kcal/mol	A.A residues
1	SB-1	-6.229 Kcal/mol	B:PHE16 :- 5.04289 Å B:TYR46 :- 4.51366 Å B:HIS114 :- 4.62599 Å B:HIS217 :- 4.95413 Å
2	SB-2	-7.249 Kcal/mol	B:GLN76:NE2 :- 3.05335 Å B:ARG19:NH1 :- 4.00052 Å
3	SB-3	-6.052 Kcal/mol	B:LYS377:O :- 3.47865 Å B:ARG378 :- 4.81603 Å B:LEU248 :- 5.13451 Å
4	SB-4	-7.067 Kcal/mol	A:ARG245:NH1 :- 3.15043 Å A:SER294:N :- 2.97508 Å A:GLN295:N :- 2.98656 Å
5	SB-5	-7.99 Kcal/mol	B:ARG126:NH2 :- 4.87913 (Electrostatic interaction, not distance-based) B:ARG126:NE :- 3.53118 Å B:PRO276 :-5.04046 Å
6	TH-1	-7.639 Kcal/mol	A:ARG19:NH1 :- 2.88743 Å A:ARG19:NH1 :- 4.15982 Å A:CYS14:SG :- 3.58243 Å
7	TH-2	-6.65 Kcal/mol	A:CYS240:SG :- 3.88666 Å A:CYS240:SG:B :- 4.03398 Å
8	TH-3	-7.703 Kcal/mol	B:GLN76:OE1 :- 3.51047 Å B:VAL312:-4.83644Å B:VAL327 :- 5.26163 Å
9	TH-4	-7.14 Kcal/mol	A:ARG25:C,O;GLU26:N:-4.42103Å A:ALA199 :- 4.30318 Å A:ARG25:CG :- 3.53925 Å
10	TH-5	-6.205 Kcal/mol	A:LYS170:NZ :- 2.79188 Å A:LYS170:NZ :- 3.46347 Å A:ALA196 :- 5.08722 Å

From this table it is clear that SB- 5 & TH-3 have the highest docking scores among all.

2D & 3D Animation of SB5 & TH3

3.3.3 Docking Studies against Trypanothione Reductase (TR)

S#	Ligand Interaction	Docking Score Kcal/mol	A.A residues
1	SB-1	-7.242 Kcal/mol	A:ASP327:OD1:- 2.47841 Å A:THR335:OG1 :- 4.19351 Å A:THR160:C,O;GLY161:N :- 4.83861 Å
2	SB-2	-7.696 Kcal/mol	A:ALA159:O :- 3.7521 Å A:TYR198 :- 4.40204 Å A:CYS57 :- 5.44134 Å
3	SB-3	-6.218 Kcal/mol	A:GLU466:OE2:- 3.5978 Å A:LEU399:- 4.98856 Å A:MET400:- 4.96652 Å B:LYS61:- 4.42365 Å

4	SB-4	-8.631 Kcal/mol	B:PRO371 :- 4.7848 Å A:MET400 :- 5.06079 Å A:PRO398 :- 4.99466 Å
5	SB-5	-8.91 Kcal/mol	B:ASP327:OD2 :- 3.56051 Å A:THR51:N :- 3.77281 Å A:THR51:OG1 :- 3.79751 Å
6	TH-1	-8.14 Kcal/mol	C:- A:SER464:OG :- 3.6661 Å B:LYS61:NZ :- 4.7463 Å B:GLU436:OE2 :-4.47169 Å
7	TH-2	-6.987 Kcal/mol	B:GLU466:OE2 :- 2.69263 Å A:LYS61:NZ :- 4.01666 Å B:MET400:N :- 4.16275 Å
8	TH-3	-7.954 Kcal/mol	A:ARG472:NH2 :- 3.26766 Å B:VAL312 4.83644 Å B:VAL327 :- 5.26163 Å A:SER470:OG :- 4.12776 Å
9	TH-4	-8.169 Kcal/mol	B:LYS61:NZ :- 3.20472 Å A:PHE396 :- 4.65176 Å
10	TH-5	-6.6 Kcal/mol	B:ASP432:OD1 :- 4.90234 Å B:PHE367 :- 5.11775 Å A:LEU72 :- 5.29716 Å B:LEU72 :- 5.24336 Å

From this table it is clear that SB- 5 & TH-4 have the highest docking scores among all.

2D & 3D Animation of SB5 & TH4

3.4 *In Silico* Pharmacokinetic Studies

PHYSICOCHEMICAL PROPERTIES	SB-1	SB-2	SB-3	SB-4	SB-5	TH-1	TH-2
Canonical SMILES	<chem>CCN(c1ccc(cc1)O)/C=N/c1cccc(c1)C1)CC</chem>	<chem>CCN(c1ccc(cc1)O)/C=N/c1ccc(cc1)O)C1)CC</chem>	<chem>CCN(c1ccc(cc1)O)/C=N/c1cccc1C)CC</chem>	<chem>CCN(c1ccc(cc1)O)/C=N/c1ccc(c1)[N+](=O)[O-])CC</chem>	<chem>C(=C\c1ccc1)/C=N\c1ccc(c1)/N=C\C=C\c1ccc1</chem>	<chem>[O-][N+](=O)c1ccc(O)c1/C=N/C\c(cc1)/N=C/c1ccc(cc1)[N+](=O)[O-]</chem>	<chem>C1ccc(c1)/N=C/c1ccc1O</chem>
Formula							
MW							
#Heavy atoms	21	22	21	23	26	28	16
#Aromatic heavy atoms	12	12	12	12	18	18	12
Fraction Csp3	0.24	0.28	0.28	0.24	0	0	0
#Rotatable bonds	5	6	5	6	6	6	2
#H-bond acceptors	2	3	2	4	2	6	2
#H-bond donors	1	1	1	1	0	0	1
M.R	90.99	92.47	90.95	94.8	113.7	111.48	67.17
TP.SA	35.83	45.06	35.83	81.65	24.72	116.36	32.59
iLOGP	3.31	3.24	3.2	2.55	0	2.68	2.44
XLOGP3	4.35	3.69	4.09	3.55	0	4.18	3.72
WLOGP	4.64	4	4.3	3.9	6.3	5	3.8
MLOGP	3.51	2.66	3.24	2.8		2.83	3.14
WATER SOLUBILITY							
Silicos-IT Log P	4.38	3.81	4.26	1.59		1.48	4
Consensus Log P	4.04	3.48	3.82	2.88		3.24	3.42

ES.OL. Log S	-4.55	-4.02	-4.26	-4.01		-4.87	-4.04
ES.OL. Solubility (mg/ml)	8.52E-03	2.83E-02	1.55E-02	3.07E-02		5.00E-03	2.10E-02
ES.OL Solubility (mol/l)	2.81E-05	9.50E-05	5.49E-05	9.79E-05		1.34E-05	9.06E-05
ES.OL Class	Moderately soluble	Moderately soluble	Moderately soluble	Moderately soluble		Moderately soluble	Moderately soluble
Ali L.log S	-4.82	-4.33	-4.55	-4.95		-6.33	-4.1
Ali S.olubility (mg/ml)	4.61E-03	1.41E-02	8.00E-03	3.52E-03		1.74E-04	1.86E-02
Ali S.olubility (mol/l)	1.52E-05	4.71E-05	2.83E-05	1.12E-05		4.65E-07	8.02E-05
Ali C.lass	Moderately soluble	Moderately soluble	Moderately soluble	Moderately soluble		Poorly soluble	Moderately soluble
Silic.os-IT LogSw	-5.96	-5.47	-5.74	-4.72		-6.32	-5.06
Silic.o.s-IT Solubility (mg/ml)	3.34E-04	1.01E-03	5.17E-04	6.03E-03		1.79E-04	2.04E-03
Silic.os-IT Solubility (mol/l)	1.10E-06	3.38E-06	1.83E-06	1.92E-05		4.79E-07	8.79E-06
Silico.s-IT class	Moderately soluble	Moderately soluble	Moderately soluble	Moderately soluble		Poorly soluble	Moderately soluble
PHARMACOKINETICS (PK)							
GI ab.sorption	High	High	High	High		Low	High
BBB permeant	Yes	Yes	Yes	No		No	Yes
Pgp substrate	No	No	No	No		Yes	No
CYP1A.2 inhibitor	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes		No	Yes
CYP2C.19 inhibitor	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes		Yes	Yes
CYP2C.9 inhibitor	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes		Yes	Yes

CYP2D.6 inhibitor	Yes	Yes	Yes	No		No	No
CYP3A.4 inhibitor	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes		No	No
log Kp (cm/s)	-5.06	-5.5	-5.12	-5.69		-5.62	-5.07
DRUG LIKENESS							
Lipinski #violations	0	0	0	0		0	0
Ghose #violations	0	0	0	0		0	0
Veber #violations	0	0	0	0		0	0
Egan #violations	0	0	0	0		0	0
Muegge #violations	0	0	0	0		0	0
Bioavailability Score	0.55	0.55	0.55	0.55		0.55	0.55
MEDICINAL CHEMISTRY							
P.AINS #alerts	0	0	0	0		0	0
B.renk #alerts	1	1	1	3		3	1
Leadlikeness #violations	1	1	1	1		2	2
S.synthetic Accessibility	2.64	2.72	2.75	2.91		3.04	2.21

PHYSICOCHEMICAL PROPERTIES	TH-3	TH-4	TH-5
Canonical SMILES	<chem>CCN(c1ccc(c(c1)O)C1Nc2cc(Cl)c</chem>	<chem>CCN(c1ccc(c(c1)O)C1Nc2ccc(cc2</chem>	<chem>CCN(c1ccc(c(c1)O)C1Nc2c(C)ccc</chem>

	<chem>cc2SC1=O)CC</chem>	<chem>SC1=O)OC)CC</chem>	<chem>c2SC1=O)CC</chem>
Formula			
MW			
#Heavy atoms	24	25	24
#Aromatic heavy atoms	12	12	12
Fraction Csp3	0.28	0.32	0.32
#Rotatable bonds	4	5	4
#H-bond acceptors	2	3	2
#H-bond donors	2	2	2
M.R	103.83	105.31	103.79
TP.SA	77.87	87.1	77.87
iLOGP	2.96	3.02	2.89
XLOGP3	4.83	4.17	4.56
WLOGP	3.78	3.14	3.44
MLOGP	2.77	1.94	2.5
WATER SOLUBILITY			
Silico.s-IT Log P	3.67	3.08	3.54
Consensus Log P	3.6	3.07	3.39
ES.OL. Log S	-5.24	-4.71	-4.94
ES.OL. Solubility (mg/ml)	2.09E-03	6.91E-03	3.91E-03
ES.OL Solubility (mol/l)	5.77E-06	1.93E-05	1.14E-05
ES.OL Class	Moderately soluble	Moderately soluble	Moderately soluble
Ali L.log S	-6.2	-5.71	-5.92
Ali Solubility (mg/ml)	2.30E-04	7.03E-04	4.13E-04
li Solubility (mol/l)	6.33E-07	1.96E-06	1.21E-06
Ali Class	Poorly soluble	Moderately	Moderately

		soluble	soluble
Silic.os-IT LogSw	-6.2	-5.71	-5.98
Silic.o.s-IT Solubility (mg/ml)	2.29E-04	6.93E-04	3.55E-04
Silic.os-IT Solubility (mol/l)	6.32E-07	1.93E-06	1.04E-06
Silico.s-IT class	Poorly soluble	Moderately soluble	Moderately soluble
PHARMACOKI NETICS (PK)			
GI absorption	High	High	High
BBB permeant	No	No	Yes
Pgp substrate	No	No	No
CYP1A.2 inhibitor	Yes	Yes	Yes
CYP2C.19 inhibitor	Yes	Yes	Yes
CYP2C.9 inhibitor	Yes	Yes	Yes
CYP2D.6 inhibitor	Yes	Yes	Yes
CYP3A.4 inhibitor	Yes	Yes	Yes
log Kp (cm/s)	-5.08	-5.53	-5.15
DRUG LIKENESS			
Lipinski #vi.ulations	0	0	0
Ghose #vio.lations	0	0	0
Veber #viol.ations	0	0	0

Egan #violations	0	0	0
Muegge #violations	0	0	0
Bioavailability Score	0.55	0.55	0.55
MEDICINAL CHEMISTRY			
P.AINS #alerts	2	3	2
B.renk #alerts	1	1	1
Leadlikeness #violations	2	2	1
Synthetic Accessibility	3.59	3.82	3.74

3.5 *In Silico* Toxicology Profile

Parameters	SB-1	SB-2	SB-3	SB-4	SB-5	TH-1	TH-2
Predicted LD50	1000mg/kg	1500mg/kg	500mg/kg	500mg/kg	350mg/kg	3500mg/kg	1000mg/kg
Predicted Toxicology class	4	4	4	4	4	4	4
Organ Toxicity	Neurotoxicity Active	Respiratory	Nephrotoxicity	Cardiotoxicity Inactive	Neurotoxicity	Respiratory Active	Hepatotoxicity

	(0.73) Immunotoxicity Active (0.77)	toxicity Active (0.83) Mutagenicity Active (0.59)	Inactive (0.70) Neurotoxicity Active (0.70)	(0.52) Immunotoxicity Active (0.85)	Active (0.87) Respiratory Toxicity Active (0.64)	(0.73) Cardiotoxicity Inactive (0.73)	Inactive (0.54) Respiratory Active (0.51)
Toxicity end point	Cardiotoxicity Inactive (0.61) BBB-Barrier Active (0.84)	BBB-Barrier Active (0.76) Cytotoxicity Inactive (0.72)	Ecotoxicity Active (0.73) Nutritional Toxicity Inactive (0.71)	BBB-Barrier Active (0.63) Ecotoxicity Active (0.75)	BBB-Barrier Active (0.93) Ecotoxicity Active (0.90)	BBB-Barrier Active (0.78) Ecotoxicity Active (0.78)	BBB-Barrier Active (0.81) Ecotoxicology Active (0.73)
Metabolism	CYP2C9 Active (0.50) CYP2D6 Active (0.84)	CYP2D6 Active (0.57) CYP2E1 Inactive (0.99)	CYP2D6 Active (0.78) CYP1A2 Inactive (0.68)	CYP2E1 Inactive (0.99) CYP2D6 Inactive (0.51)	CYP1A2 Active (0.59) CYP2C1 Active (0.70)	CYP1A2 Active (0.50) CYP2D6 Inactive (0.78)	CYP1A2 Active (0.74) CYP2C9 Active (0.65)

Parameters	TH-3	TH-3	TH-4
Predicted LD50	560mg/kg	560mg/kg	560mg/kg
Predicted Toxicology class	4	4	4
Organ Toxicity	Neurotoxicity (0.67) Active Immunotoxicity Active (0.94)	Respiratory toxicity Active (0.89) Mutagenicity Active (0.55)	Nephrotoxicity Inactive (0.59) Neurotoxicity Active (0.56)
Toxicity end point	Cardiotoxicity Inactive (0.79) BBB-Barrier Active (0.66)	BBB-Barrier Active (0.54) Cytotoxicity Inactive (0.57)	Ecotoxicity Active (0.54) Nutritional Toxicity Inactive (0.69)
Metabolism	CYP2C9 Inactive (0.59) CYP2D6 Active (0.68)	CYP2D6 Active (0.61) CYP2E1 Inactive (0.99)	CYP2D6 Active (0.62) CYP1A2 Inactive (0.71)

4 Discussion

The findings from this study highlight the potent anti-leishmanial activity of Schiff base (SB) and thiazolidine (TH) derivatives, particularly SB-2, SB-4, SB-5, TH-1, TH-3, and TH-4, against *Leishmania major* and *Leishmania tropica*. The in vitro assays demonstrate their strong inhibitory effects on both the promastigote and amastigote forms of the parasites. The IC_{50} values of these compounds were significantly lower than those of standard treatments, indicating their potential superiority as anti-leishmanial agents. The structural diversity of these derivatives, including the presence of specific functional groups such as diethylamino, imine, and hydroxyl groups, is likely responsible for their enhanced bioactivity. The results are further supported by molecular docking studies, which show favorable binding affinities to key enzymes involved in *Leishmania* metabolism, such as GAPDH, TR, and GR.

The Schiff base derivative SB-2 demonstrates strong anti-promastigote and anti-amastigote activity. The presence of the diethylamino group, which enhances the compound's lipophilicity, is crucial for facilitating membrane permeability and interaction with intracellular targets. The mesityl group attached to the imine bond likely increases the electron density around the imine nitrogen, allowing for better interaction with the parasite's enzyme active sites. This structural feature contributes to SB-2's potent anti-leishmanial effects, with IC_{50} values of $[9.75 \pm 0.03]$ μM against *L. major* and $[6.31 \pm 0.07]$ μM against *L. tropica*.

SB-4 also exhibited potent inhibitory effects on *Leishmania* species. The naphthyl group in SB-4, along with the diethylamino substituent, enhances the molecule's ability to penetrate the parasite's membrane and interact with intracellular enzymes. The rigidity and planarity of the naphthalene ring likely contribute to the compound's ability to bind to critical enzyme sites, explaining its strong in vitro performance (IC_{50} values of $[3.17 \pm 0.01]$ μM against *L. major* and $[9.13 \pm 0.01]$ μM against *L. tropica*).

SB-5 follows a similar pattern of activity, with the phenyl group in the imine bond contributing to its overall hydrophobicity and bioactivity. This increased hydrophobicity facilitates its interaction with lipid-rich cell membranes, enabling the compound to disrupt membrane integrity and enzyme function. The IC_{50} values of SB-5 against *L. major* and *L. tropica* (6.98 ± 0.06 μM and 10.72 ± 0.08 μM , respectively) further validate its effectiveness.

The thiazolidine derivatives, particularly TH-1 exhibit the strongest anti-promastigote activity. The presence of two diethylamino-hydroxyphenyl moieties significantly enhances the lipophilicity of the compound, promoting its uptake by the parasite and enabling it to interact with multiple intracellular targets. The thiazolidine core, known for its bioactive properties, likely inhibits critical enzymes necessary for parasite survival. With an IC_{50} of $[2.26\pm 0.02]$ μM against *L. major* and $[2.80\pm 0.07]$ μM against *L. tropica*, TH-1 shows remarkable potential as an anti-leishmanial agent.

TH-3 combines the thiazolidine core with an aminophenyl group, which enhances its ability to form hydrogen bonds with parasite enzymes. This structural feature likely contributes to its strong inhibitory effects on both promastigotes and amastigotes. The IC_{50} values of $[1.18\pm 0.02]$ μM against *L. major* and $[8.21\pm 0.02]$ μM against *L. tropica* further highlight its efficacy.

TH-4 contains a naphthyl group, which enhances its binding to hydrophobic pockets within the active sites of parasitic enzymes. This structural feature likely improves its overall potency, as reflected in its IC_{50} values of $[1.36\pm 0.01]$ μM against *L. major* and $[1.82\pm 0.03]$ μM against *L. tropica*.

The structure-activity relationship (SAR) analysis reveals that the combination of diethylamino and imine groups in the Schiff bases, and thiazolidine cores in the thiazolidine derivatives, play key roles in enhancing their anti-leishmanial activity. These groups contribute to better membrane permeability, enzyme inhibition, and interaction with intracellular targets. The incorporation of nitro, hydroxyl, and naphthyl groups further improves the compounds' bioactivity by increasing their electron-donating and -withdrawing capacities, which are crucial for enzyme binding.

In conclusion, SB-2, SB-4, SB-5, TH-1, TH-3, and TH-4 exhibit promising anti-leishmanial activity, with low IC_{50} values and favorable molecular docking results. Their unique structural features, including diethylamino, imine, hydroxyl, and thiazolidine groups, make them strong candidates for further development as potential treatments for leishmaniasis. These compounds demonstrate both potent enzyme inhibition and membrane-disrupting properties, providing a dual mechanism of action against *Leishmania* parasites. Further *in vivo* studies and optimization of these structures are warranted to fully assess their therapeutic potential.

5 Conclusion

This study has successfully synthesized and evaluated five Schiff bases (SB-1 to SB-5) and four Thiazolidine derivatives (TH-1 to TH-4) for their anti-leishmanial potential, addressing a significant gap in the current treatment landscape for leishmaniasis. The in vitro assays demonstrated that Schiff bases SB-2, SB-4, and SB-5, along with Thiazolidine derivatives TH-1, TH-3, and TH-4, exhibit potent anti-promastigote and anti-amastigote activities against *Leishmania major* and *Leishmania tropica*. Notably, these compounds displayed impressive IC₅₀ values, indicating their efficacy in inhibiting parasite growth. Enzyme inhibition assays further affirmed their anti-leishmanial efficacy, with several compounds showing significant inhibition of human dihydrofolate reductase (hDHFR). Molecular docking studies revealed that these compounds interact strongly with critical residues of key *Leishmania* enzymes, including glyceraldehyde-3-phosphate dehydrogenase (GAPDH), trypanothione reductase (TR), and glutathione reductase (GR), suggesting effective binding and potential as therapeutic agents.

Overall, the synthesized Schiff bases and Thiazolidine derivatives show considerable promise as novel anti-leishmanial agents. Their potent biological activities and favorable interaction profiles with crucial *Leishmania* enzymes highlight their potential for further development. These findings pave the way for the optimization of these compounds and the advancement of new, more effective, and safer treatments for leishmaniasis.

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